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Project DOI

[10.17605/OSF.IO/SX3AV](https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SX3AV)

https://doi.org/10.35542/osf.io/6prfb_v1

Author Contribution The author is solely responsible for the conception, design, protocol development, intervention planning, and manuscript drafting of the e-Motiva-PREV pilot cluster-RCT.

INTRODUCTION AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The e-Motiva-PREV program is scientifically grounded in two widely validated change models:

- Self-Determination Theory (SDT): The program aims to satisfy basic psychological needs (Autonomy, Competence, Relatedness) to foster Autonomous Motivation (intrinsic/identified). According to SDT, internalization of motivation serves as a strong protective factor against deviant and antisocial behavior, promoting proactive behavioral control (Ryan & Deci, 2017; Vansteenkiste et al., 2020).

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- Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT): CBT components focus on training Emotional Regulation skills (Gross, 2015) and Impulse Control. The program specifically targets Hostile Attribution Bias (HAQ), a core cognitive deficit in aggressive youth (Dodge & Pettit, 2003). By correcting HAQ, the program teaches Cognitive Reappraisal of ambiguous situations, reducing the likelihood of reactive aggression (Lochman et al., 2015). The efficacy of CBT in universal school-based interventions for conduct problems is supported by meta-analytic evidence (Durlak et al., 2011).

METHODS

Study Design

The study employs a cluster-randomized controlled trial (cluster-RCT) design with assessments conducted at three time points (T0, T1, and T2).

Participants

The study includes a total of 10 classes (clusters) from 8th and 9th grades, with approximately 329 students ($N \approx 329$).

- Inclusion Criteria: 8th/9th-grade students with signed Informed Consent Forms by parents or guardians.
- Randomization: The 10 classes will be randomly assigned to Intervention Group (IG) (5 classes, $N \approx 165$) and Control/Waitlist Group (CG/WL) (5 classes, $N \approx 164$).

Sample justification: Based on previous studies conducted in Portuguese school contexts (e.g., Durlak et al., 2011; Veiga, 2020), the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) is estimated between 0.03 and 0.06, which informs the required sample size for multilevel analysis and justifies the number of clusters in this pilot study.

Intervention (Program Description)

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e-Motiva-PREV consists of 10 weekly sessions of 50 minutes, administered by a Psychologist (Lead Facilitator) together with the Class Teacher (Co-Facilitator). The program focuses on introducing and practicing the SDT and CBT change mechanisms, including mindfulness exercises and ambiguous social problem-solving.

The program is structured in three modules—“My Path,” “My Emotions,” and “My Strength”—with each module addressing distinct pedagogical objectives aligned with school competencies. The sequential allocation of sessions, pedagogical focus, and alignment with curriculum competencies are summarized in Table 1.

The sequential details of activities for each session, the time allocated per phase (Check-in, Core Activity, Conceptualization), and the fidelity monitoring protocol are fully described in Appendix A: Detailed Intervention Manual of the e-Motiva-PREV Program.

Assessment Measures (Instruments)

The validity and rigor of this Cluster Randomized Controlled Trial (cluster-RCT) depend on the use of measurement instruments with established psychometric validity, adapted to the Portuguese adolescent population whenever possible. Assessments will be conducted at three time points (T0, T1, T2) to measure primary outcomes, which validate the program’s preventive efficacy, and secondary outcomes, which evaluate the theoretical change mechanisms (SDT and CBT).

A. Primary Outcomes (Preventive Efficacy)

Primary outcomes include self-reported delinquent behavior and hostile attribution bias, assessed using validated instruments specifically adapted for Portuguese adolescents. Complete anonymity is ensured to maximize honesty in reporting, and the instruments target the key cognitive and behavioral mechanisms of

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change promoted by the program (see Table 2 for details of primary and secondary measures).

B. Secondary Outcomes (Theoretical Change Mechanisms and Functional Indicators)

The secondary outcomes of the e-Motiva-PREV pilot cluster-RCT, including autonomous motivation, emotion regulation, well-being, resilience, psychosocial adjustment, and functional academic performance, are summarized in Table 3. These measures assess both theoretical mechanisms of change (SDT and CBT) and functional indicators relevant to adolescent development and school adjustment.

Fidelity Analysis

Fidelity of program implementation is assessed using the Process Fidelity Checklist (see Table 4).

Data Analysis Plan

Data will be analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 30.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). All analyses will follow the Intention-To-Treat (ITT) principle, including all participants regardless of the actual dose of intervention received.

Baseline group characteristics will be compared using Student's t-tests or chi-square tests, depending on the nature of the variables.

Preliminary intervention efficacy will be assessed using Hierarchical Linear Models (HLM), suitable for nested data (level 1: individual; level 2: class), complemented by Generalized Estimating Equations (GEE) for sensitivity analyses. The HLM will be specified as a two-level mixed model, with random intercepts for cluster (class) and fixed effects for group, time, and group \times time interaction. This structure allows modeling intraclass dependence among participants within the same class, ensuring robust estimates of longitudinal intervention effects.

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The intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) will be calculated to estimate variance attributable to the cluster level and to confirm the adequacy of sample assumptions outlined in Section 4.2 (Participants).

Given the limited number of clusters ($n = 10$), analyses are exploratory, focusing on preliminary ICC and effect size estimates without confirmatory hypothesis testing. Time \times group effects will be interpreted based on adjusted marginal effect estimates, reporting two-tailed p-values, 95% confidence intervals, and Cohen's d effect sizes. Mediation analyses (e.g., the mediating role of emotion regulation or satisfaction of psychological needs) will be conducted using non-parametric bootstrapping with 5,000 resamples and bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals, following Preacher and Hayes (2008). Multilevel mediation models (Preacher, Zyphur, & Zhang, 2010) may complement these analyses depending on sample size and data stability.

Missing data will be handled using Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations, assuming a Missing at Random (MAR) mechanism. The Benjamini–Hochberg False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction will be applied exploratorily to balance type I error control with the risk of type II error in small pilot samples.

This protocol follows the SPIRIT guidelines (Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials) for cluster-RCTs, ensuring transparency, methodological rigor, and reproducibility. In the final trial report, CONSORT recommendations will be followed to ensure comprehensive and accurate reporting of study outcomes.

All analyses will be reviewed by an independent statistician to verify appropriateness of methods, assumptions, and consistency of results before submission for scientific publication in a high-impact, peer-reviewed journal (e.g., *Prevention Science*).

Ethics and Risk Procedures

The e-Motiva-PREV study was authorized by the Administration of the Agrupamento de Escolas de Esmoriz Ovar Norte (Internal Order No. 1/2025), ensuring institutional feasibility and collaboration with teaching staff and the Psychology and Guidance Service (SPO).

The protocol will be reviewed by the Ethics Committee of one University in Portugal, to ensure compliance with national and international ethical standards for research with minors in school settings.

Participation is entirely voluntary, ensuring confidentiality, anonymity, and the right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Informed consent from guardians and assent from students (13–16 years old) will be obtained to guarantee fully informed participation (see Annex C for documents).

The Risk Protocol defines procedures in case of confidentiality breach or imminent risk to the participant or others, with immediate notification to guardians and school administration. Strict confidentiality of self-reported delinquency (SRD) and other sensitive measures is maintained in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; EU 2016/679).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS**Scientific and Educational Implications**

The e-Motiva-PREV program is grounded in a robust theoretical and institutional framework, providing high potential for impact and sustainability. Scientifically, the intervention integrates two well-validated change models: Self-Determination Theory (SDT), promoting intrinsic motivation and satisfaction of basic psychological needs as key protective factors, and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), essential for emotion regulation training and correction of Hostile Attribution

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Bias, a proximal mechanism of reactive aggression. This strategic combination targets both motivational processes (autonomous motivation) and cognition (hostile bias).

Practically, the program fully aligns with the Ministry of Education guidelines, addressing Well-Being, Health, and Safety competencies in the Student Profile and fitting within the Personal and Interpersonal Development area of the National Strategy for Citizenship Education (ENEC), facilitating future integration as a universal school-based preventive tool.

Study Limitations and Methodological Challenges

Pilot Study Design Limitations

- **Feasibility vs. Definitive Efficacy:** The primary aim is to assess feasibility (retention, fidelity, logistics) and estimate parameters (Effect Size and ICC) for a future full-scale RCT. Consequently, the small pilot sample limits generalization of preliminary efficacy results.
- **Short Follow-up Period:** Participant follow-up is limited to three months (T2), precluding evaluation of long-term maintenance of behavioral and motivational effects (e.g., 6 or 12 months).

Implementation and Fidelity Challenges

- **Co-Facilitation Dependence:** Program delivery relies on class teachers as co-facilitators. Intervention efficacy is sensitive to their training, intrinsic motivation, and adherence to manualized CBT/SDT techniques. Low adherence or withdrawal of a co-facilitator may compromise integrity of an entire cluster.
- **Contamination Risk:** Cluster allocation may lead to content sharing between intervention and control groups within the same school.

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- Logistical Challenges and Absenteeism: Allocating 10 sessions of 50 minutes across the school year is subject to calendar variability. High absenteeism or interruptions may reduce actual intervention dose, affecting efficacy testing.

Measurement and Bias Considerations

- Social Desirability Bias: Key outcomes (delinquency, violence, Hostile Attribution Bias) are self-reported. Adolescents may respond in socially acceptable ways, underestimating real psychosocial risk.
- Non-Specific Effects: The control/waitlist group does not isolate the specific effect of the e-Motiva content from non-specific attention or group participation effects.

Methodological Summary

Despite pilot limitations, inclusion of analytic controls—ICC calculation, ITT principle, multiple imputation, and Benjamini–Hochberg FDR correction—maximizes internal validity and robustness of exploratory inferences.

Future Research Directions

Feasibility data and preliminary efficacy estimates will inform a future full-scale RCT, including a substantially larger number of schools. A long-term follow-up (T3, e.g., 6–12 months post-T2) is crucial to confirm sustainability of behavioral, emotional, and motivational gains. This pilot provides a solid methodological foundation for program expansion.

DISSEMINATION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER PLAN

Academic Dissemination (External Validation)

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The main vehicle for external validation will be publication in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals specialized in Educational Psychology, Clinical Psychology, Development, or Risk Prevention (e.g., *Prevention Science*).

Findings will also be presented at national and international conferences as oral or poster communications.

Community and Institutional Dissemination (Sustainability)

A detailed technical-scientific report will be shared with school administration and the Serviços de Psicologia e Orientação (SPO), summarizing efficacy results, fidelity analysis, and practical implications. Results will be presented at faculty council meetings to assess potential integration of e-Motiva-PREV methods into the ENEC curriculum, ensuring continuity and project legacy.

DECLARATIONS

Funding

The authors did not receive support from any organization for the submitted work. No specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors was received.

Disclosure of potential conflicts of interest

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

Ethical approval

The e-Motiva-PREV study protocol will be submitted to the Ethics Committee of the..., Portugal. All procedures to be performed will be in accordance with the ethical

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standards as laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. The study was authorized by the Administration of the Agrupamento de Escolas de Esmoriz Ovar Norte (Internal Order No. 1/2025).

Informed consent

Written informed consent will be obtained from all legal guardians, and written assent will be obtained from all adolescent participants (13–16 years old) included in the study.

Clinical Trial Registration

Not applicable. This manuscript describes the protocol for an exploratory pilot cluster-RCT focused primarily on assessing feasibility and parameter estimation (Effect Size and ICC). Consequently, this pilot study does not require prospective registration as a definitive trial. Full-scale future trials will be registered.

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